

1 **Resistance to TNF-alpha blockade.**

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7 Resistance in cancer to clinical intervention is arguably intelligent and assumed to be a function of
8 selection pressure and mutagenic potential of cancer. Resistance in immune disease to targeted therapies
9 (where selective pressure has not been similarly studied) is less well understood. We studied
10 compensatory responses in humans with immune disease following a cytokine targeted therapy by
11 measuring total transcription in autoimmune and inflammatory disease treated with infliximab or
12 adalimumab. We performed a transcriptomic expression screen using primary cells and tissues from
13 humans with autoimmune disease using Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) as a discovery model for TNF
14 interventions in immune disease. We compared the blood or synovial tissue at baseline or following
15 treatment with a TNF-a inhibitor and compared total transcription based on whether an acceptable
16 treatment response has been achieved. The expression screen identified hundreds of genes as candidate
17 genes that together control resistance to TNF inhibition in humans. Genes associated with cellular
18 identity, whose expression is presumed or likely to be a function for homeoboxes factors, TCF/Lef nuclear
19 signaling through the Wnt pathway and TLE co-repressors, along with other nuclear factors define
20 disease specific expression “barcodes” were prominent among those described here. Resistance in
21 chronic immune disease like RA and IBD, despite absence of selective pressure resulting from
22 transformation, reflects a collection of gene expression changes that describe the existence of
23 re-established homeostatic thresholds for acceptable signaling and transcription within a pathologic
24 system.
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1 **Results**

2 GSE1051: RA, whole blood, baseline, responders vs non-responders; infliximab

3 GSE15602: RA, synovial biopsy, good vs. poor response; adalimumab.

4 GSE3592: RA, PBMC, infliximab

5 Control PBMC vs non-responders

6 Control PBMC vs responders

7 GSE66207: Fibroblasts, terminal ileum, CD. B1 and B2 versus B3 phenotype.

8 GSE99817: Large intestine, CD. B1 and B2 versus B3 phenotype.

9 GSE190349: RA, random n=10 v n=10 patient only transcriptome comparison. CD4+ blood cells.

10 SH3-domain

11 Soluble effectors

12 TNF superfamily

13 Prostaglandin, leukotrienes and lipoxygenase

14 Nuclear factors

15 Factors that specify cell or developmental identity

15 Factors that control a signal or specific function rather than specify identity

16 Epigenetic molecules

17 Oncogenes

18 Homeobox factors

19 Autophagy

20 Cell death

21 Mitochondria and ATP

22 Energy: AKT, MTOR and PI3K

23 Secretory pathway, cellular degradation and vesicular trafficking

23 Lysosome

24 ER

24 Golgi

25 Peroxisome

25 Protein folding and modifications

26 Vesicle transport

27 Ubiquitin and proteasome

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1	Odorant receptors and related receptor pathways
2	TAAR
	ODR4-relayed
3	Cell cycle
4	Tumor suppression
5	Nucleotide synthesis
6	Carbohydrate and polysaccharide metabolism
7	Phospholipase and cAMP signaling
8	Glycoproteins
9	Immune receptors
10	Developmental
	Stem cell signaling
11	Morphogens
12	Chemotaxis associated
13	Antibacterial
14	Antigen presentation, self non-self discrimination and tolerogenic signaling
15	Calcium signaling
16	Proteases and peptidases
17	DNA damage and repair
18	Metabolic
	Glycolytic
19	Fatty acid and hydrocarbon
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21	Non-coding RNAs
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